

AN ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF PRESCHOOL TEACHERS' FLOW LEVELS ON PROFESSIONAL JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract:

The forms of organizational regulation expressed by "Human Resources Management" started to come up after 1980s, and as a result, the concept of "work related flow", which is a positive attitude towards the act of working, gained currency. Based on this concept, the purpose of the present research is investigating whether the people who have flow experience pleasure and excitement while working. 278 pre-school teachers working in pre-school education institutions affiliated to Düzce Provincial Directorate of National Education constitute the universe of the present research conducted in the relational screening model. The work group consisted of 162 preschool teachers who were selected by convenient sampling method. "Job Satisfaction Scale" developed by Kuzgun, Sevim and Hamamcı (2005) and "Work-related Flow Scale" developed by Yalçinkaya (2013) were utilised as data collection tools of the present research. According to the findings of the present research, there is a positive relationship between the teachers' flow motivation and Job Satisfaction levels. In addition, there is a significant difference between the flow levels of teachers, employment, seniority, number of students in the class variables.

Keywords: work related flow, job satisfaction, pre-school

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1. Introduction

The act of working is a concept that involves more than just making money and labouring in return. Therefore, the meaning attached to "act of working" shapes the individual's life. One of the concepts that have been discussed in the context of human resources management and organizational behaviour in recent years is the concept of "work related flow", which is a sub-branch of workaholism. This concept, which has been studied as of the late twentieth century, become a subject of interest as a result of the emergence of policies aimed at providing the maximum benefit from human resources at work (Çaldağ, 2010; Albayrak, 2012; Yalçınkaya, 2013).

Being absorbed in something or a job refers to almost isolation from everything else, and feeling an endless enjoyment and happiness of what is done. Csikszentmihalyi (2000), who coined the concept of work related flow, defined this concept as "*being absorbed in the job with intrinsic feelings and feeling high level of enjoyment and happiness from the work done*".

Job satisfaction, which is closely related to the concept of work related flow, refers to the enjoyment and happiness of one's job and all other factors related to the job. In other words, job satisfaction is a sum of one's work-related emotional reactions. Job satisfaction is also defined as "*the state of emotional enjoyment created by the work related experiences and the values attached to work*" (Houkes, 2003; Ekin, 2010).

If work related flow provides happiness, does experiencing flow in work life increase individuals' Job Satisfaction? This present research studies the relationship between the concepts of 'enjoyment', 'Job Satisfaction' and 'work-related flow' which constitute the psychological dimensions of the act of working in terms of preschool teachers.

2. Method

2.1 Research Model

The purpose of the present research is defining the relationship between pre-school teachers' levels of work related flow and Job Satisfaction levels and examining the effects of flow on Job Satisfaction. Another purpose of the present research is determining whether there is a meaningful relationship between the demographic features of pre-school teachers and their levels of flow and Job Satisfaction. In accordance with these purposes, the present research is designed in relational screening model. Relational screening model aims at determining the existence and degree of mutual change between more than one variable (Karasar, 2009).

2.2 Universe and Sample

278 pre-school teachers working in the schools affiliated to Düzce Provincial Directorate of National Education form the universe of the present research. 162 pre-school teachers selected by convenient sampling method form the sample of the present research. Considering the 95% confidence interval and 0.05 error margin, this number can

represent the pre-school teachers who work in the province selected for the universe of the research. Convenient sampling refers to including individuals in the immediate vicinity, who are easy to access, available, and volunteering to participate in the research, in the sample when a certain region does not matter (Erkuş, 2013). The distribution of pre-school teachers participating in the present research by their demographic features is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distributions of Teachers by Demographic Features

	Categories	f	%
Employment	Tenured	112	69.1
	Contracted or paid	50	30.9
Seniority	5 years and less	54	33.3
	6-10 years	78	48.1
	11 years and more	30	18.5
Number of students in the class	15 and less	62	38.3
	16-20	58	35.8
	21 and more	42	25.9
Total		162	100.0

According to Table-1 presents the distribution of pre-school teachers by their demographic features. According to the employment status, there are 112 tenured (69.1%) and 50 contracted or paid (30.9%) teachers. According to seniority, there are 54 teachers (33.3%) with "5 years or less" seniority, 78 teachers (48.1%) with "6-10 years" seniority and 30 teachers (18.5%) with "11 years or more" seniority. According to number of students in class, there are 62 teachers (38.3%), who have "15 and less1 students in their class, 58 teachers (35.8%) with "16-201 students and 42 teachers (25.9%) with "21 and more" students.

2.3 Data Collection Tools

Personal information form developed by researchers to determine the demographic features of pre-school teachers during the collection of research data includes employment, professional seniority and number of students in the class variables.

A. Job Satisfaction Scale

"Job Satisfaction Scale" developed by Kuzgun, Sevim and Hamamcı (2005) was used to define the Job Satisfaction levels of teachers. The scale consists of 20 five-point Likert type items. The items relate to the ability of people to comply with the interests and abilities of their professional activities, to take responsibility, to develop and promotion opportunities. Positive items numbered 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20 are scored as; always = 5, often = 4, occasional = 3, rarely = 2 and never = 1, the remaining negative items are scored as the opposite. The lowest score from the test is 20, while the highest score is 100. As the scores from the scale increase, the Job Satisfaction level increases as well. In order to determine the validity of the scale, factor analysis technique was used by Kuzgun, Sevim and Hamamcı (2005) and it was determined that

the items of the scale were divided into two dimensions as "Eligibility to Qualifications" and "Desire to Develop". The total variance explained by the two dimensions was 48.6%, the variance explained by the first dimension was 36.4%, and the variance explained by the second dimension was 12.2%. The internal consistency coefficient was calculated for the reliability of the scale. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the whole scale is .90.

B. Work Related Flow Scale

The scale adapted to Turkish by Yalçınkaya (2013) in order to reveal the work related flow levels of pre-school teachers was first developed by Bakker et al. (2005) in the USA and used to measure the work related flow levels of the employees. The scale consisting of a total of 13 items is scored on a 7-point Likert type scale (1 = never, 2 = almost never, 3 = sometimes, 4 = from time to time 5 = frequently, 6 = very often, 7 = always). These refer to the employees' motivation for absorption and enjoyment from work. Scale scores provide information on employees' work related emotional state, concentration and flow levels. It was adapted to Turkish by Yalçınkaya in 2013 and proven to be valid and reliable for Turkish Labour Market. The sample of the research conducted for Turkish adaptation consisted of a total of 84 employees working in a state bank in Turkey. Of these 84, 43 (51.1%) were female and 41 (48.9%) were male. The average age of female employees was 29.04 and the average age of male employees was 30.14. Work related flow scale consists of two dimensions. The first dimension includes items numbered 1, 2, 3, 4, 9 and 13 and explains to motivation for absorption. The second dimension includes items numbered 5, 7, 8, 10, 11 and 12 and explains to motivation for enjoyment from work. Absorption dimension explains the 13.18% of the variance, and enjoyment dimension explains the 48.32% of the variance. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficients were calculated as .85 and .87, respectively.

2.4 Data Analysis

The data collected from the pre-school teachers for the present research were processed in the SPSS package program. First, the distributions of the data were examined and it was found that there were no extreme values and no data showing the missing data problem. Subscales of the flow scale were defined as independent variables and the score distribution of job satisfaction scale as dependent variables. Whether there was a multiple connection problem among the independent variables was tested in the regression analysis process and Pearson correlation analysis result between two subscales of flow scale was found as $r = .96$. This result showed a multiple connection problem as it was above the critical value of .90 (Albayrak, 2012). For this reason, subscales of flow scale were combined and analysed as a single dimension. Simple linear regression analysis was used instead of multiple regression analysis since there was a single independent variable. Normality and Levene's homogeneity tests were performed to determine whether the data distribution was parametric or nonparametric, before studying the differences between the simple linear regression

analysis conducted to reveal the relationship between the scales and the scores obtained from the teachers' demographic features and scores from scales. In order to test the normality assumption, the values of skewness and kurtosis of scores obtained from teachers' job satisfaction scale and flow scale were analysed and found to be between -1 and +1. As a measure of the normality assumption, the skewness and kurtosis coefficients being between -1 and +1 is stated to be acceptable (Morgan, Leech, Gloeckner, Barrett, 2004). According to the homogeneity of the test variances, i.e. the distribution of the Levene homogeneity test results, the homogeneous distribution of the test variances is achieved according to Levene Statistic $p > .05$. The distribution of scores obtained from the scales is continuous data and they are at equal interval scale level. That two samples (groups) are independent from each other, that dependent variables are measured at interval or ratio scale level, assumptions of normality and homogeneity are met, meet parametric test assumptions (Köklü, Büyüköztürk, Bökeoğlu, 2007). The relationship between the scales applied to preschool teachers was examined by Pearson Correlation analysis. A simple linear regression analysis was conducted to study the effects of teachers' flow motivation on job satisfaction levels. Independent-Sample t-test was used to determine whether there was a significant difference between the motivation for flow and job satisfaction levels in terms of the employment status of preschool teachers. One-Way ANOVA was used to determine whether there was a significant difference between the scores of the teachers in terms of their seniority and the number of students in their classes. Multiple-comparison (Post Hoc) Tukey test (Can, 2014) was used in the one-way analysis of variance used to compare groups when there was a significant difference between the variables with more than two groups.

3. Findings and Interpretation

First Sub-Problem: Is there a relationship between pre-school teachers' the motivation for flow and their job satisfaction levels?

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Analysis Results for
 the Relationship between Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Flow

		Absorption	Enjoyment
Job Satisfaction	r	.77(*)	.73(*)
	p	.000*	.000*
	N	162	162

* $p < .05$

As presented in Table 2, there is a high level of positive correlation between the pre-service teachers' flow motivation and job satisfaction levels according to $r = .77$, $p = .000 < .05$. Flow motivation explains the 59% of teachers' job satisfaction ($r^2 = .77 \times .77 = .59$). There is a high level of positive correlation between the pre-service teachers' enjoyment

motivation and job satisfaction levels according to $r = .73$, $p = .000 < .05$. Enjoyment motivation explains 53% of teachers' job satisfaction ($r^2 = .73 \times .73 = .53$).

Second Sub-Problem: Does pre-school teachers' flow motivation have any effects on their job satisfaction levels?

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results for the Effects of Teachers' Flow Motivation on their Job Satisfaction Levels

Variable	B	Standard Error B	β	T	p	binary r
Constant	25.07	2.56		9.78	.000*	
Flow	0.69	0.05	0.75	14.45	.000*	0.75
R= .75 R ² =0.57						
F= 208.92 p=.000*						
Equation: Job Satisfaction =25.07+.69*Flow						

*p<.05

As presented in Table 3, flow motivation of pre-school teachers is a significant predictor of their job satisfaction according to $F = 208.92$, $p = .000 < .05$. Teachers' flow motivation explains 57% of their job satisfaction. The effect of preschool teachers' flow motivation on job satisfaction is significant according to $t = 14.45$, $p = .000 < .05$. The value of binary correlation between the two variables is .75.

Third Sub-Problem: Is there any difference in the flow motivation of preschool teachers in terms of employment?

Table 4: Independent-Sample T-Test Results on the Difference in Flow Motivation of Teachers in terms of Employment

Dimensions	Employment	N	$\bar{X}$	S	t	sd	p
Absorption	Tenured	112	26.42	6.69	3.86	160	.000*
	Contracted or paid	50	22.30	5.23			
Enjoyment	Tenured	112	28.29	6.43	3.93	160	.000*
	Contracted or paid	50	23.82	7.23			

*p<.05

As presented in Table-4; there is a significant difference in absorption dimension in terms of employment according to $t_{(160)} = 3.86$, $p = .000 < .05$. This significant difference results from the fact that tenured teachers have higher absorption than contracted or paid teachers. There is a significant difference in enjoyment motivation dimension in terms of employment according to $t_{(160)} = 3.93$, $p = .000 < .05$. This significant difference results from the fact that tenured teachers have higher enjoyment motivation than contracted or paid teachers.

Forth Sub-Problem: Is there any difference in job satisfaction levels of preschool teachers in terms of employment?

Table 5: Independent-Sample T-Test Results on the Difference in Job Satisfaction Levels of Teachers in terms of Employment

Scale	Employment	N	$\bar{X}$	S	t	sd	p
Job Satisfaction	Tenured	112	66.17	11.32	10.47	160	.000*
	Contracted or paid	50	49.28	1.71			

*p<.05

As presented in Table-5; there is a significant difference in job satisfaction levels of preschool teachers in terms of employment according to $t_{(160)} = 10.47$, $p = .000 < .05$. This significant difference results from the fact that tenured teachers have higher job satisfaction than contracted or paid teachers.

Fifth Sub-Problem: Is there any difference in the flow motivation of preschool teachers in terms of seniority?

Table 6: One-Way Variance (ANOVA) Analysis Results on the Difference in Flow Motivation of Teachers in terms of Seniority

Dimensions	Seniority	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F(2-159)	p	Post Hoc (Tukey)
Absorption	5 years and less	54	24.76	7.33	11.86	.000*	2>3, 1>3
	6-10 years	78	27.12	5.56			
	11 years and more	30	20.73	5.17			
Enjoyment	5 years and less	54	27.37	7.88	12.06	.000*	2>3, 1>3
	6-10 years	78	28.58	6.06			
	11 years and more	30	21.73	4.86			

*p<.05 Categories: 5 years and less =1; 6-10 years =2; 11 years and more =3

As presented in Table-5; there is a significant difference in absorption motivation dimension in terms of seniority according to $F_{(2-159)}=11.86$, $p=.000<.05$. This significant difference results from the fact that teachers with “5 years and less” seniority have higher absorption than teachers with “6-10 years” and “11 years and more” seniority.

There is a significant difference in enjoyment motivation dimension in terms of seniority according to $F_{(2-159)}=12.06$, $p=.000<.05$. This significant difference results from the fact that teachers with “5 years and less” seniority have higher enjoyment motivation levels than teachers with “6-10 years” and “11 years and more” seniority.

Sixth Sub-Problem: Is there any difference in job satisfaction levels of preschool teachers in terms of seniority?

Table 7: One-Way Variance (ANOVA) Analysis Results on the Difference in Job Satisfaction Levels of Teachers in terms of Seniority

Scale	Seniority	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F(2-159)	p	Post Hoc (Tukey)
Job Satisfaction	5 years and less	54	62.00	14.66	2.99	.053	
	6-10 years	78	62.11	12.00			
	11 years and more	30	56.07	5.56			

*p<.05 Categories: 5 years and less =1; 6-10 years =2; 11 years and more =3

As presented in Table-7, there is a significant difference in job satisfaction levels of teachers in terms of seniority according to $F_{(2-159)}=2.99$, $p=.000<.05$. This significant difference is between teachers with “5 years and less”, “11 years and more” seniority and teachers with “11 years and more” seniority.

Seventh Sub-Problem: Is there any difference in the flow motivation of preschool teachers in terms of number of students in their class?

Table 8: One-Way Variance (ANOVA) Analysis Results on the Difference in Flow Motivation of Teachers in terms of Number of Students

Dimensions	Number of Students	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F(2-159)	p	Post Hoc (Tukey)
Absorption	15 and less	62	24.35	6,53	5,45	.005*	2<3, 1<3
	16-20	58	23.98	6,16			
	21 and more	42	27.93	6,42			
Enjoyment	15 and less	62	26.11	7,19	7.03	.001*	2<3, 1<3
	16-20	58	25.36	6,50			
	21 and more	42	30.21	6,31			

* $p<.05$ Categories: 15 and less =1; 16-20 =2; 21 and more =3

As presented in Table-8; there is a significant difference in absorption motivation dimension in terms of number of students according to $F_{(2-159)}=5.45$, $p=.000<.05$. This significant difference results from the fact that teachers with “15 and less” students have lower absorption motivation than teachers with “16-20” and “21 and more” students.

There is a significant difference in enjoyment motivation dimension in terms of number of students according to $F_{(2-159)}=7.03$, $p=.000<.05$. This significant difference results from the fact that teachers with “15 and less” students have lower enjoyment motivation than teachers with “16-20” and “21 and more” students.

Eighth Sub-Problem: Is there any difference in job satisfaction levels of preschool teachers in terms of number of students in their class?

Table 9: One-Way Variance (ANOVA) Analysis Results on the Difference in Job Satisfaction Levels of Teachers in terms of Number of Students

	Number of Students	N	$\bar{X}$	S	F(2-159)	p	Post Hoc (Tukey)
Job Satisfaction	15 and less	62	59.06	1.56	7.45	.001*	2<3, 1<3
	16-20	58	58.60	1.37			
	21 and more	42	67.00	1.98			

* $p<.05$ Categories: 15 and less =1; 16-20 =2; 21 and more =3

As presented in Table-9; there is a significant difference in job satisfaction levels of teachers in terms of number of students according to $F_{(2-159)}=7.45$, $p=.000<.05$. This significant difference results from the fact that teachers with “15 and less” students

have lower job satisfaction levels than teachers with “16-20” and “21 and more” students.

4. Discussion, Conclusions and Suggestions

Organizational justice perceptions, professional enjoyment, working conditions, promotion and personal possibilities, job security, and wage levels are positive for employees who experience work related flow. (This statement is argumentative, it may not be true). It is known that individuals who have a high degree of work related flow and commitment do not seek another job, are committed to their organization and enjoy their jobs, since they have positive feelings about their work.

According to a general evaluation of the findings of the present research, there was a positive correlation between the flow motivation and the job satisfaction levels of teachers. In addition, it was found that there was a significant difference in the levels of flow in terms of employment, seniority, and number of students in the class.

According to the results obtained from the research; the relationship between pre-school teachers' flow and job satisfaction is striking. Work related flow motivation affects the job satisfaction of teachers positively. This finding is in agreement with the findings of the previous studies on the subject (Wrzesniewski, Rozin and Bennett, 2002; Richardson, Simmering and Sturman, 2009; Conway and Lance, 2010; Rich, Simmering, Sturman, 2010).

Additionally, according to similar studies on the subject, work related flow levels are high among individuals working in creative, non-routine jobs is high while work related flow levels are low in routine jobs requiring automation (Greenberg and Baron, 2000; Lyness and Judiesch, 2001; Gruman and Saks, 2011). Based on this information, it is possible to reach the conclusion that the pre-school teachers experience work related flow in jobs they enjoy and experience satisfaction, and therefore work related flow levels and job satisfaction levels predict each other.

In the present research, job satisfaction and work related flow levels of the teachers were examined separately in terms of employment and it was found that there was a significant difference in terms of employment in both of the variables. That tenured preschool teachers have a higher level of job satisfaction and flow than the contracted or paid teachers is expected. According to previous studies in agreement with the present research, improvements made in the personal rights have positive effects on both job satisfaction and work related flow (Ashforth and Humphrey, 1993; Csikszentmihalyi, 1997; Gray and Smith, 2009; Hwang, Kou, 2006).

The finding obtained in the present research that pre-school teachers' work related flow and job satisfaction levels decrease as their seniority increases suggests that in time productivity and efficiency of teachers decreases and therefore their work related flow and enjoyment are repressed along with this. There are many studies in the related literature with findings in agreement with this finding (Schaubroeck and Jones, 2000; Barutçugil, 2002; Gray and Smith, 2009).

Pre-school teachers' work related flow motivations and job satisfaction levels decrease as the number of students in their classes decrease, which presents the positive effects of crowded classes. Accordingly, as the number of students in pre-school teachers' classes increases, their work related flow and job satisfaction levels are affected positively. Similar studies in the related literature show that classes are adversely affected by too high or too little classroom size, while average classroom size is appropriate (Celep, 2002; Zurawsky, 2003; Ferguson, 1991).

The finding that young teachers with low seniority, who have more students in their classes and a satisfactory employment (tenured), have higher levels of work related flow is a unique contribution of the present research to both the national and international literature.

According to the findings of the present research, it would be appropriate to reinforce the work related flow levels besides their job satisfaction and accordingly to improve teachers' personal rights in order to increase the efficiency and productivity of pre-school teachers.

It is stated that many external factors besides personality, which is an internal, factor affect job satisfaction and work related flow, and these external factors are working environment, organizational climate, social relations, family, culture and so on. In order to increase the levels of job satisfaction and work related flow of preschool teachers, it would be a good practice to enhance conditions such as classroom size and employment way, which can also be among the external factors mentioned above.

The concepts of "job satisfaction" and "work related flow" are subjects that have not been studied together much in the academic literature. For this reason, there are many areas that can be investigated and many factors that can be associated. Further studies can investigate the relationship between work related flow and job satisfaction focusing on specific occupations. It is believed that work related flow may be affected by a number of factors other than "job satisfaction", which is an internal factor. For this reason, it is suggested that further studies are conducted by establishing relationships with different external factors.

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